

INNOVATIVE-PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS FOR INCREASING THE MANAGEMENT POTENTIAL OF DEPUTY DIRECTORS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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The methodological basis of this study is the theories of pedagogy, educational management, and innovative management. During the study, local and foreign scientific literature, regulatory and legal documents, and best practices were analyzed

ABSTRACT

This thesis is devoted to highlighting the role and importance of innovative pedagogical mechanisms in increasing the managerial capacity of deputy principals in preschool educational institutions. These mechanisms serve to develop deputy directors' strategic thinking, decision-making, analytical approach, and leadership competencies. Observation method – when analyzing management processes in preschool educational institutions; Comparison method – when comparing the effectiveness of traditional and innovative management mechanisms.

The results of the study showed that the introduction of digital technologies, the use of electronic management systems, and the establishment of analytical monitoring significantly increase the management potential of deputy directors. It is also necessary to improve the system of advanced training, revise curricula, and widely introduce practice-oriented modular training to implement these mechanisms. In general, innovative pedagogical mechanisms can improve the quality of management in preschool educational institutions, is an important factor in developing the professional potential of leaders and ensuring the effectiveness of education. Bush T. Educational management and leadership. - London, 2011 ovoid pedagogical mechanisms, digital technologies, educational management, competence-based approach, analytical monitoring.

The following methods were used in the research process:

- Scientific analysis and synthesis – in studying and summarizing the theoretical foundations of innovative-pedagogical mechanisms;

- Observation method – when analyzing management processes in preschool educational institutions;
- Questionnaire and interview – when identifying the opinions and experiences of deputy directors regarding management activities;
- Diagnostic assessment – in determining the level of management potential and competencies;
- Comparison method – in comparing the effectiveness of traditional and innovative management mechanisms.

The results of the study showed that the introduction of digital technologies, the use of electronic management systems, and the establishment of analytical monitoring significantly increase the management potential of deputy directors. Also, the project-based management, reflection and indicator-based assessment system have a positive effect on the strategic development of leaders.

Conclusion.

The results of the study showed the importance of innovative pedagogical mechanisms in increasing the management potential of deputy principals in preschool educational institutions. The effective use of digital technologies, electronic management systems, and analytical monitoring tools in the management process will take the activities of managerial personnel to a new level.

Innovative and pedagogical mechanisms, in particular project-based management, systematic reflection and indicator-based assessment systems, develop strategic thinking, analytical approach and leadership competencies of deputy directors. This serves to improve management efficiency.

It is also necessary to improve the system of advanced training, revise curricula, and widely introduce practice-oriented modular training to implement these mechanisms. Creating digital learning platforms based on competencies ensures the continuous professional development of leadership personnel.

In general, innovative-pedagogical mechanisms are an important factor in improving the quality of management in preschool educational institutions, developing the professional potential of leaders, and ensuring the effectiveness of education.

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